

THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN ENSURING CLIMATE CHANGE AND WATER USE

Dilafroz Aliqulova

Head of the Department of Human Resource Development and management of the Ministry of water management of the Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10734778>

Abstract. *The article highlights the fact that climate change is one of the most difficult problems of our time, the existing gap between the population, including the further strengthening of gender inequality, the fact that in the process of combating climate change around the world, gender issues are not removed from the agenda, issues that affect climate change are one of the factors affecting everything*

Keywords: *climate, sustainable development, gender equality, agriculture, natural disasters, sanitation, health, nature, water, land, assets and services, convention.*

Introduction. Climate change is one of the most pressing challenges of our time, exacerbating existing disparities between populations, including gender inequality. Therefore, in the process of combating climate change around the world, it is observed that this issue is becoming an important direction in the gender agenda.

It is known that the 13th paragraph of the Sustainable Development Goals until 2030 stipulates taking urgent measures to combat climate change. Climate change continues to be one of the factors affecting all of the Sustainable Development Goals. In particular, climate change is preventing people from ending poverty by depriving them of regular sources of income (BRM 1), adversely affecting agriculture and increasing the threat to food security (BRM 2). At the same time, this situation has a direct negative impact on human health (BRM 3). However, natural disasters cause the death or maiming of thousands of people, the spread of diseases transmitted through food and water. There is evidence that climate change is also having a negative impact on people's mental health. In turn, deterioration of socio-economic living conditions limits people's access to quality education (BRM 4). Climate change will also negatively affect access to water resources, sanitation (BRM 6) and energy (BRM 7). Its dire consequences are unemployment and deprivation of a regular source of income, forcing many people to move (migration) in search of a source of livelihood and new work ((BRM 8).

Gender issues are increasingly discussed in the Conferences of the Parties (COPs) of the UN Convention on Climate Change. In particular, the Human Rights Council, based on its Resolution No. 38/4 dated 28.06.2019, held a discussion on "Women's rights and climate change: climate action, best practices and lessons learned. "Issues of climate change have gained special importance for Uzbekistan, and our country is among the vulnerable countries with a high degree of influence on this painful problem. The shortage of water resources, the salinization of water and soil, and the increase in soil erosion have already become one of the serious problems. Currently about 20% of the country's population (6 million people) suffer from water salinity and high mineralization, and the drying up of the Aral Sea is exacerbating the ongoing situation.

Due to climate change, special attention is being paid in our country to the issue of ensuring the use of water. Climate change is reducing access to clean water, affecting its quality and sanitation infrastructure, resulting in a build-up of polluted water. Climate change is seriously

affecting people's access to food, clean drinking water and sanitation, health and medicine, education, decent housing and secure employment. All this has a negative impact on the health of women and girls, especially pregnant women, who are the most vulnerable.

Analysis. Women themselves are stakeholders in agricultural water management, playing an important role in water and land resource management and efficient use, rainwater harvesting, and watershed resource allocation. Women are active in both irrigated and dryland agriculture, including two-thirds of dryland food production in many developing countries where women outnumber men. According to the latest estimates of the UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), the number of women employed in the agricultural sector of developing countries is 43%. At the same time, there is a misconception that the majority of farmers in agriculture are men, which undermines the role of women in water management.

The importance of ensuring equal use and control of water use, including the involvement of men and women in water management in agriculture, is widely recognized by the international community. The 1995 Beijing Platform for Action called on governments to develop knowledge and research on the role of women, especially rural and indigenous women, in irrigation, watershed management and sanitation.

In the "Political Declaration and Agenda for the 21st Century" adopted by the UN Conference on Environment and Development in Rio de Janeiro in 1992, the important role of women in the efficient use of the environment and ensuring their equal participation in decision-making on water resources management and women - it is emphasized that it is necessary to reduce the workload of girls. Also, in the final document of Rio+20, in order to end poverty, the obligation to gradually ensure access to safe and affordable drinking water for all, which is important for the protection of public health, was emphasized once again. The importance of the role of women in the management of water resources is also noted in the documents adopted in many political processes. In particular, the UN Mar del Plata Water Conference in 1977, the International Decade of Drinking Water Supply and Sanitation (1981–1990), the International Conference on Water Resources and Environmental Protection held in Dublin in 1992, the Road Map in Johannesburg in 2002, etc. among them. The founding resolution of the International Decade of Action on Water for Life (2005–2015) also calls for the inclusion and participation of women in water-related aspects of development activities.

The General Assembly's November 2011 Resolution "On the Advancement of Rural Women" calls on member states to ensure access to safe and clean drinking water and sanitation services to improve the health of rural women and children.

Water management policies and processes often ignore the water needs of women and men and their gender inequalities.

Irrigation access is often associated with disproportionate land rights, negatively affecting the productivity and incomes of smallholder women food farmers.

Summary. Women are often excluded from decision-making processes in water resources management. To achieve gender equality in the use of water resources in agriculture, it is necessary to recognize the role of women as farmers or irrigators and provide them with equal participation in production resources, services and decision-making. As a result:

- recognition of women as independent water users and ensuring their right to use water regardless of land ownership.

- by supporting the role of women as water managers, farmers and irrigators, the efficiency of water and food resources management will be increased and the rights and opportunities of women in the water and food supply system will be expanded;
- through the introduction of labor-saving technologies, the unpaid labor burden of women in collecting water, producing and processing food products, and maintenance will be eased;
- eliminate many forms of gender discrimination in the use and control of production resources such as water and land, assets and services;
- Water services will be improved by initiating reforms that address the water needs of poor families, especially women-led farms in rural areas;
- training skills for water management, irrigation, rainwater harvesting and other irrigation technologies will be created for women engaged in small farming;
- measures and reporting indicators are formed to encourage women's leadership in the use of water resources in agriculture, including gender audit;
- The capacity of government, civil society and other stakeholders to understand and address gender issues in the use and management of water resources in agriculture will be strengthened.

REFERENCES

1. en WHO calls for climate action for a sustainable recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic// <https://www.who.int/ru/news/item/11-10-2021-who-s-10-calls-for-climate-action-to-assure-sustained-recovery-from-covid-19>
2. The Conference of the Parties, known as the COP, is the decision-making body responsible for monitoring and reviewing the implementation of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. It brings together 197 countries and territories, called Parties, that have acceded to the Framework Convention. The COP has met annually since 1995. The 21st session of the Conference of the Parties (COP 21), which took place in Paris, France, in December 2015, was historic in its outcome - the first international climate agreement.
3. The first National Communication on climate change of the UN Interim Convention. - Tashkent, 1999.
4. Khikmatov Bekzod Fazliddinovich, Pirmazarov Ravshan Topvoldievich
5. Calculation of the outbreak discharges through a closure channel with trapezoid shape of cross-section // European science review. 2018. №7-8. [URL:https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/calculation-of-the-outbreak-discharges-through-a-closure-channel-with-trapezoid-shape-of-cross-section](https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/calculation-of-the-outbreak-discharges-through-a-closure-channel-with-trapezoid-shape-of-cross-section) (дата обращения:14.05.2022).3.
6. National document on the status of environmental resources and use of natural resources in the Republic of Uzbekistan (1988-2007). (2008). - Tashkent. -298 p.
7. Ososkova, T.A., Spektorman, T.Yu., Chub, V.E. (2006). Climate change. - Tashkent. OZGIMET. -54 s.
8. Water is an important vital resource for the future of Uzbekistan. Publication in support of the Millennium Development Goals. Goal 7: "Ensuring ecological sustainability" of the UN Development Program. (2007). Tashkent. -136 p.
9. Resolution adopted by the Human Rights Council on July 5, 2018, 38/4. Human rights and climate change.